

Teaching Effectiveness of Women Teachers in Relation to their Emotional Intelligence

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence is considered as expressing, understanding and managing emotions in individuals as well as in others. It is a blend of heart and mind. Emotional Intelligence is a skill to observe, manage and evaluate emotions. Emotional intelligence involves various characters such as social precision, self-awareness, to understand the others feeling, to face strong emotions, the capacity to wait for the enjoyment, to be positive in case of difficulty. There are five essentials components in emotional intelligence; they are Self-regulation, Self-awareness, Motivation, Empathy and Social skills. In the present scenario, the proposal of emotional intelligence among the teachers takes greater attention in the present educational system.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, Teaching Effectiveness, Self-awareness

Introduction

Emotional Intelligence acts as an important role in social science. Emotional knowledge, intelligence and skill plays an important role in education and helping students, teachers, faculties to attain higher degrees of achievement, career success, leadership and personal wellbeing. It rules the teacher's behavior and it is important for the achievements in their profession. Teachers are regarded as the main pillar in the teaching organization. They also considered as mediators, because through them only the knowledge is passed to the students. They are the effective source of knowledge because they possess the essential skills, knowledge and talents. Emotional Intelligence involves a healthy emotional behavior. It includes various characters such as thinking, finding, managing and expressing feelings. Emotional Intelligence enables the individuals to react at the right place, right time and for the right purpose in a right way.

In this place, emotional intelligence makes a person to look through the problem and they can search for a key to that problem. Teaching is a traumatic occupation. Teachers lead a life with a time of speedy revolution and increased stresses. This may be tough for teachers to stay healthy and effective in challenging work atmospheres unless they absorb and execute positive stress management abilities regularly.

In the midst of this backdrop, the present study clearly focuses in identifying the phenomena related to the emotional intelligence of college teachers in colleges which affiliated to Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai. It helps to build social relationships and managing emotions.

Emotional Intelligence and Teaching

Goleman stated that the expression of emotional intelligence in the classroom and school have a great impact on learners development. When a teacher acts without EI in the classroom, students feel emotionally weak, “hijacked”, which causes a negative impact on their learning. Emotionally intelligent teachers are very active in their profession, family and throughout their life. They will overcome very easily in any difficult situation. Teachers who purposely develop emotional skill and emotional behavior experience more achievements and fulfillment in their educational organization and life. Teachers with high level of emotional intelligence can handle their own emotions well.

Emotional Intelligence Progress Has Two Wide Purposes

1. The feelings of the teachers and students should be recognized and responded.
2. The emotional state in the learner should be encouraged.

Generally, teaching is an emotional practice which includes emotional understanding, emotional labor and emotional relationships. It requires teachers to develop into more efficient models in terms of emotional intelligence. Emotionally intelligent teachers are active in their orientation to pupils, effort, and life. The pupils and educators have several problems in their lives; these problems become a major disruption in classrooms across the nations. So that it is very vital to progress emotional and social skills by the tutor at the education organization. Because it can have a good academic achievement not only during the year they taught, but during the years that follows as well. Due to all these reasons a vast importance and needs are required for examining the emotional intelligence of teacher educators.

Teaching is acknowledged is one of the vital and demanding occupations in the contemporary society. Without any disputes, teachers play a major role in student achievement and learning these professionals convey the knowledge and also ensure that students gain the learning skills to culturally and socially relevant behaviours. Therefore teaching job considered as is a job of high “emotional labour” and the considerable evidence documents significant level of the occupational stress which is experienced by the teachers (Not a continued Foot note) which results in mental health difficulties and job dissatisfaction. Hence, the psychological healths of the teachers are quite imperative for “success” of the students, education system and larger society.

Emotional Intelligence and Teacher’s Performance

Emotional understanding, skill and cleverness are a major thing in improving education and helping students, teachers and faculties. Emotional intelligence is vital important in all the fields because it speculate victory in all ways of life. The students and teachers have many difficulties in their lives; these difficulties become a major interruption in classrooms across the nations. So that it is very important to develop emotional and social skills by the teacher at the education institution. Because it can have a good academic achievement not only during the year they taught, but during the years that follows as well. Due to all these reasons a huge importance and needs are

required for investigating the emotional intelligence of teacher educators. The positive outcome of achievements, goal achievement, and personal wellbeing builds the human development behaviors. Emotional intelligence is a key for building this human development behavior. An emotional knowledge program is effective in improving emotional knowledge and ability of tutors a good tutor needs an understanding of single and group motivation and personality to make an educational surroundings that creates positive social communication, active commitment and the motivation to learn.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are as follow:

1. To identify the level of Emotional Intelligence and its specific components among the college teachers
2. To analyze the various factors determining the emotional intelligence among the college teachers.

Analysis of Variance Table for One Way ANOVA

**Table 1 One way ANOVA
ANOVA for Experience of the Women Teachers and Getting Feedback
From the Students After Their Lecture**

TE.3					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.149	4	3.037	4.526	.003
Within Groups	43.622	65	.671		
Total	55.771	69			

As significance value is (0.003) less than the .05, one concludes at a 95 percent confidence level that the null hypothesis might be rejected, and there is a significant relationship between the experience of the women Teachers and getting feedback from the students after their lecture.

**Table 2 One Way ANOVA
ANOVA for Age Group of the Women Teachers and they Take Care on
Students Responses at the Time of Teaching**

TE.9					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.827	3	.276	.744	.530
Within Groups	24.445	66	.370		
Total	25.271	69			

As significance value is (0.530) greater than the .05, one concludes at a 95 percent confidence level that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, and there is no significant relationship between the age group of the Women Teachers and they take care on students responses at the time of teaching.

Table 3 One Way ANOVA
ANOVA for Educational Qualification of the Women Teachers and They Use Various Teaching Methods for Different Subjects

TE.14					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.524	2	2.262	3.844	.026
Within Groups	39.419	67	.588		
Total	43.943	69			

As significance value is (0.026) less than the .05, one concludes at a 95 percent confidence level that the null hypothesis might be rejected, and there is a significant relationship between the Educational Qualification of the women teachers and they use various teaching methods for different subjects.

Major Findings

- Overwhelming 97 % (Strongly Agree 59% + Agree 38%) of the teachers have agreed with give practical examples to the students in the course of their teaching.
- Great majority 91% (Strongly Agree 50% + Agree 41%) of the women teachers have agreed that they change their teaching methodology based on students' responses.
- A large majority 88 % (Strongly Agree 40 % + Agree 48 %) of the teachers agreed that they help the students to give correct answers through their teaching.
- Maximum number of the teachers 94 % (Strongly Agree 63% + Agree 31%) have agreed that when they repeat their lecture if the students do not understand the subject.
- Overwhelming 91 % (Strongly Agree 43 % + Agree 48%) of the teachers agreed they are asked questions to stimulate thinking the power of the students.

Conclusion

Teachers are the most significant resource in education reconstruction. Teaching effectiveness is the scope in which the teaching activity completes its proposed purpose, function, and goals. A teacher needs an awareness of his/her feelings, values and attitudes as a teacher, awareness of her behavior and how others see them. Consistent and constructive feedback from the students, colleagues, and authorities facilitate a teacher in better self-evaluation of her abilities. Those with better emotional intelligence have no uncertainty in taking the feedback from others and then working to constantly progress their performances.

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